

Open Energy Family

Current and Planned Developments

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Goal:

Better research through transparency and reproducible data management in energy system analysis

Existing tools:

- Open database for energy data
- API and OEDialect
- Data Upload Wizard
- Fact sheets for frameworks, models and scenarios
- Open Energy Ontology

Ongoing Developments :

- Data versioning
- Scenario Explorer
- OEKG
- Open Data Peer Review
- Databus

Contributions:

- Upload open data
- Add and improve metadata
- Review other metadata and data

Open Energy Family – History

Contributions: **Commits** ▾

- Open community database for energy climate and modelling data
 - Status: 1000+ data tables
 - Planned: Constant maintenance and clean-up

- Platform and web interface
 - Status: Redesign and usability
 - Planned: More frontend for existing tools + OEO

- Fact sheets for frameworks, models and scenarios
 - Status: 20+ frameworks and 200+ models
 - Planned: Scenarios using the Ontology and Knowledge Graph

- Tutorials, manuals and example code
 - Status: 30 tutorials
 - Planned: Train-the-trainer and documentation

- Metadata standard
 - Status: Release of v1.5.1 in progress (Ontology ready)
 - Planned: Use of the Knowledge Graph

- A common open energy data model for energy and scenario data
 - Status: Used for model comparisons and mappings (IAMC...)
 - Planned: New metadata version and ontology links

- SQLAlchemy dialect using the REST-API
- Status: Easy to use; additional tools available (e.g. OEM2ORM)
- Planned: Bugfixes and support of additional data types

- Metadata integration to process and translate OEMetadata
- Status: Release of v1.5.1 in progress
- Planned: Mappings to other standards like DCAT-AP

- Process integration, data pipelines and data review
- Status: 100+ datasets under review (GitHub process)
- Planned: Move process to the OEP, display with data

- Ontology - a formal collection of terms
 - Status: 1000+ issues; 2000+ classes (terms)
 - Planed: Integrate and improve [OEO-Viewer](#)

- Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG)
 - Status: First prototypes under development
 - Planed: Factsheets, Scenario Comparisions

- Data pipelines (open_MaStR) and helper tools (OEM2ORM, SAIO)
 - Status: Used for automations
 - Planed: Update, integrate, and documentation

Summary:

- A flexible and comprehensive framework for RDM
- Used and improved by an active community
- Integrated tools (Database / Metadata / Ontology)
- High-Scores at FAIR und 5 Stars LOD

„The opposite of **‘open’** isn’t **‘closed’**. The opposite of **‘open’** is **‘broken’**.“

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